

Applying Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process to Evaluate the Emotional Perception of Cultural and Creative Products

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Abstract

In order to promote product identity in the global market, many companies had used the strategy of associating products with cultural features. Since it was recognized that the image of such kinds of products plays an important role of its success, it is essential to evaluate alternative design solutions based on the emotional response of target users. Although some literature had indicated that there were different levels or categories of emotion, no specific hierarchy of criteria had been developed for evaluating the emotional responses of cultural and creative products. Therefore, the objective of this research is to develop a systematic approach for decision making at the stage of conceptual design. In order to construct the hierarchy of emotion, the authors conducted survey on relevant literature and collected data from interviewing experienced professors and designers. In addition, since the developed criteria tended to be vague, the fuzzy AHP approach was employed to obtain the overall ratings of design alternatives. Furthermore, this approach was demonstrated using a case study related to designing cultural and creative products in Keelung City, a northern harbor in Taiwan. The results showed that this approach not only provided a structured way of decomposing a complex decision-making problem but also avoid using crisp scores while translate the voice of customers in evaluating concepts at early design stage.

Conference theme: Teaching across cultures design

Keywords: Cultural and Creative Industry, Emotional Design, Fuzzy AHP (FAHP)

1. Introduction

In order to promote product identity in the global market, many companies had used the strategy of associating products with cultural features. In Taiwan, the cultural and creative industry plays a crucial role especially in the knowledge-based economy. This approach had contributed to increasing the value of traditional products and facilitating the promotion of local culture.

Since the image of such kinds of products plays an important role of its success, it is essential to evaluate alternative design solutions based on the emotional response of target users. Although some literature had indicated that there were different levels of pleasure or different categories of emotion, no specific hierarchy of criteria had been developed for evaluating the emotional responses of products that belong to the cultural and creative industry. Therefore, the objective of this research is to develop a systematic approach for decision making at the stage of product concept design. Detailed methods are discussed in the following sections.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Emotional design of cultural products

Based on the idea of hierarchy of needs from Maslow in 1943, Jordan (1999) identified three levels of user needs in product features, i.e. functionality, usability, and pleasure. In his theory, pleasure can be further classified as socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure, ideo-pleasure, and physio-pleasure. From emotional points of view, Norman (2004) proposed a framework for analyzing products in a holistic way to include their attractiveness, their behavior, and the image they present to the user - and of the owner. These different aspects of a product were identified with different levels of processing by people: visceral, behavioral, and reflective. These three levels translate into three different kinds of design. Visceral design refers primarily to that initial impact, to its appearance. Behavioral design is about look and feel -- the total experience of using a product. And reflection is about ones thoughts afterwards, how it makes one feel, the image it portrays, the message it tells others about the owner's taste. These concepts were valuable and further applied to develop the design model for cross-cultural products (Lin, 2007).

Furthermore, in order to measure the emotional responses of using products, Desmet (2003) developed several versions of measuring instruments, named PrEmo. PrEmo is a non-verbal self-report instrument that measures 14 emotions that are often elicited by product design. Of these 14 emotions, seven are pleasant (i.e. desire, pleasant surprise, inspiration, amusement,

admiration, satisfaction, fascination), and seven are unpleasant (i.e. indignation, contempt, disgust, unpleasant surprise, dissatisfaction, disappointment, and boredom). Instead of relying on the use of words, respondents can report their emotions with the use of expressive cartoon animations.

In the field of Human Computer Interaction, some projects had attempted to provide the platform for measuring emotions (Boehner et al., 2007). In order to quantify emotion while playing computer games, some researchers presented a fuzzy approach for continuously modeling emotion using physiological data (Mandryk and Atkins, 2007).

Although the emotional power of products has been emphasized recently, there was not enough research addressing the fuzziness of measuring emotions for cultural products in the design practice. Furthermore, although emotional design had been considered to create cultural products (Lin, 2007), the hierarchy of emotions was not applied to the evaluation of these design concepts. It was recognized emotion responses had hierarchy and should be considered (Table 1).

Authors	Aspects	Hierarchy or dimension
Jordan, P.W.(2000)	benefits associated with products	practical, hedonic, emotional
Tiger, L. (1992); Jordan, P.W.(2000)	four different kinds of pleasure	physiological pleasure, social pleasure, psychological pleasure ideological pleasure
Jordan, P.W.(1999)	hierarchy of user needs	functionality, usability, pleasure
Norman,D.A.(2004)	three characteristics of an object	visceral: how visually attractive it is; behavioural: how well it functions; reflective: whether stories can be told about it
Khalid and Helander (2004)	customer emotional needs in product design	holistic impression, functionality, design details (styling)

Laros and Steenkamp(2005)	four positive basic emotions	Contentment, Happiness, Love, Pride
Ortony et al. (1988); Desmet and Hekkert (2002)	three central variables that determine the valence of the resulting emotion	The desirability of an event, The praiseworthiness of an act, The attractiveness of an object,
Leong and Clark (2003)	framework for studying cultural objects	outer "tangible" level, mid "behavioral" level, inner "intangible" level.

Table 1: The hierarchy and dimensions of emotion

2.2 Fuzzy AHP

The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) was first introduced by Saaty (1980). It has become a popular technique to solve unstructured problems in different areas of multi-criteria decision making, such as political, economic, social and management sciences (Vaidya and Kumar, 2004). Since product design is also multi-solution problem affected by various factors such as the functions, aesthetics, and usability etc., using a systematic method to evaluate the priorities among the related factors is necessary. Lin et al. (2007) proposed a consultative AHP method to evaluate the relationships between customer requirements and design characteristics.

Using AHP in solving a decision problem involves three phases (Saaty, 1980; 2000), that is, (1) problem decomposition (hierarchical) (2) evaluation phase (comparative judgment – pairwise comparisons) and (3) synthesis of alternatives (ranking). The AHP uses pairwise comparisons to compare elements under given conditions and then converts vague verbal response into a 9-point linguistic scale. In AHP, multiple paired comparisons are based on a standardized evaluation scheme (1=equal importance; 3=weak importance; 5= essentially importance; 7=very strong importance; 9=absolute importance).

AHP provides a methodology to calibrate the numeric scale for the measurement of quantitative as well as qualitative performances. However, AHP is thus ineffective when applied to ambiguous problem (Chang et al., 2008). Since the real world is highly ambiguous, Laarhoven and Pedrycz (1983) have evolved Saaty's AHP into the FAHP, bringing the triangular fuzzy number of the fuzzyset theory directly into the pairwise comparison matrix of the AHP.

There are many recent studies have integrated fuzzy theory and AHP to support decision-making in various fields. For example, Lee et al. (2008) integrated a fuzzy AHP and BSC approach for evaluating performance of IT department in the manufacturing industry in Taiwan. Chen et al. (2007) has constructed a fuzzy AHP with MDS in identifying the preference similarity of alternatives. Hsieh et al. (2004) employed fuzzy AHP for selecting of planning and design tenders in public office building. Furthermore, in design related fields, Wu et al. (2004) were using FAHP process on optimum spatial allocation and Ma et al. (2007) also using FAHP for customized product color combination. In this paper, the author proposed a method to help Keelung City Cultural Bureau in selecting cultural and creative design solutions by using Fuzzy AHP to convert the human linguistic into triangular fuzzy numbers for emotional perception assessment. Steps in the FAHP with of this study are proposed in next section.

3. Methods

3.1 Hierarchical structure of evaluation criteria

In order to develop a hierarchy of criteria for evaluating cultural and creative products from emotional perspectives, the authors invited two university professors and one senior designer to participate in a focus group. Based on intensive literature review and after weeks of discussion, the hierarchy of emotion perception for such types of products was constructed (Figure 1).

The goal of evaluation is emotional satisfaction. The major criteria consist of four items, i.e., scenario attractiveness (S), tangibility (T), affective satisfaction (A), and reflection (R). Scenario attractiveness can be further decomposed into the degree of immersion and the topicality about product stories. These stories include where, when, why, and how this product was from and the relationship among products, people, and places. Tangibility includes attractiveness characteristics of the product itself, including lovable, elegant, conspicuous, and delicate features. Affective satisfaction is the state of emotion when a person owns the product. These states include contented, delightful, and prideful emotions. Reflection refers to the potential social interactions of using the product, including recallable and sharable experiences.

Figure 1: The hierarchical framework for S.T.A.R. evaluation criteria

3.2 Fuzzy judgment matrix

Since the criteria for evaluating the emotional perception of cultural products might have differences in their importance, the authors used linguistic variable of expression to compare two criteria by 5 basic linguistic and 4 intermediate terms. In other words, the fuzzy judgment matrix and weight vector were represented as $\tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \tilde{3} \dots \tilde{9}$. In this paper, the membership functions of these fuzzy numbers were defined in Table 2. The fuzzy judgment matrix was then used to record the relative importance of pairwise comparison between two criteria. The matrix can be represented as follows.

$$\tilde{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{a}_{12} & \cdots & \tilde{a}_{1n} \\ \tilde{a}_{21} & 1 & \cdots & \tilde{a}_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{a}_{n1} & \tilde{a}_{n2} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{a}_{12} & \cdots & \tilde{a}_{1n} \\ 1/\tilde{a}_{12} & 1 & \cdots & \tilde{a}_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ 1/\tilde{a}_{1n} & 1/\tilde{a}_{2n} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Fuzzy number	Linguistic Scale	Positive triangular fuzzy numbers
$\tilde{9}$	Absolutely important (Ab)	(8,9,9)
$\tilde{8}$	Intermediate	(7,8,9)
$\tilde{7}$	Very strongly important (Vs)	(6,7,8)
$\tilde{6}$	Intermediate	(5,6,7)
$\tilde{5}$	Essentially important (Es)	(4,5,6)
$\tilde{4}$	Intermediate	(3,4,5)
$\tilde{3}$	Weakly important (Wk)	(2,3,4)
$\tilde{2}$	Intermediate	(1,2,3)
$\tilde{1}$	Equally important (Eq)	(1,1,2)

Table 2: Triangular fuzzy numbers

3.3 Fuzzy weights and synthetic utility values

According to the definitions of linguistic variables, the authors employed fuzzy geometric mean to integrate the fuzzy performance score from all evaluators.

$$\tilde{a}_{ij} = (\tilde{a}_{ij}^1 \otimes \tilde{a}_{ij}^2 \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{ij}^n)^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

In addition, the geometric mean technique defined by Buckley (1985) was used to obtain the fuzzy geometric mean and fuzzy weights of each criterion.

$$\tilde{r}_i = (\tilde{a}_{i1} \otimes \tilde{a}_{i2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{in})^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{w}_i = \tilde{r}_i \otimes (\tilde{r}_1 \oplus \tilde{r}_2 \oplus \dots \oplus \tilde{r}_n)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

In Equation 3, \tilde{a}_{ij} is the fuzzy comparison value of criterion i to criterion j , and \tilde{r}_i is the geometric mean of fuzzy comparison value of criterion i to each criterion. In Equation 4, \tilde{w}_i is the fuzzy weight of the i th criterion, that can be expressed by a triangular fuzzy number, $\tilde{w}_i = (lw_i, mw_i, uw_i)$.

3.4 Defuzzification, overall weights and ranking

The result of the fuzzy synthetic decision reached by each alternative is a fuzzy number. Therefore, it is necessary that a nonfuzzy ranking method for fuzzy numbers be employed for comparison of each criterion. In other words, the procedure of defuzzification is necessary to locate the Best Nonfuzzy Performance value (BNP). Methods of such defuzzified ranking generally include mean of maximal (MOM), center of area (COA), and α -cut. Among these methods, COA is simple and practical (Hsieh et al, 2004). The procedure of defuzzification in

this study was to employ the center of area (COA) method derived from Teng and Tzeng (1996) .

$$DF_{wi} = \frac{(uw_i - lw_i) + (mw_i - lw_i)}{3} + lw_i \quad (5)$$

Moreover, in order to compare the importance of different criteria, the authors need to normalize the weight vector for each criterion.

$$NW_i = \frac{DF_{wi}}{\sum DF_{wi}} \quad (6)$$

After the weights of elements at all levels are computed, the authors need to sequence the overall level hierarchy weight and calculate the overall weight:

$$OW_k = NW_i \times NW_{ip} \times NW_{ipk} \quad (7)$$

In Equation 7, OW_k is the overall weight of alternative k . NW_i is the normalized weight of i criterion at top level. NW_{ip} is the normalized weight of the p sub-criterion of i criterion at the second level. NW_{ipk} is the normalized weight of alternative k of with respect to the p sub-criterion at the lowest level.

According to the value of the overall weights for each criterion, the ranking of alternatives can then be processed.

4. An Illustrative Example

4.1 A decision-making problem of Keelung City Cultural Bureau

In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method, the authors used an illustrative example relevant to designing cultural and creative products in Keelung City, a northern harbor in Taiwan. There were profound culture and historical heritages behind actual landscapes in Keelung area. However, traditional marketing approaches failed to expand their publicity and attractiveness. Hence, a design consultancy consist of students from design college developed and proposed three different design solutions including Beer Festival at Bisha Fishing Port, Chinese Halloween Festival and the Legend of Hoping Island for Keelung (see Fig. 2).

The concept of Beer Festival at Bisha Fishing Port was to memorize the golden age in 1950's. At that time, Bisha harbour was a vacation and supplying centre of U.S. navy. The crew enjoyed Taiwanese Beer and had a good relationship with citizens.

The history of Chinese Halloween Festival in Keelung has evolved for over 150 years. The activities of sacrificial ceremony, parade, and lamp floating down the river are bustling on the July of lunar calendar. However most of these activities are held in limited duration. The passion of people vanishes as the festival terminates. Therefore, the design team proposed a series of exclusive mascots and amulets for Chinese Halloween Festival to promote this festival as a long term and the most famous folk activity in Keelung.

Hoping Island, the gateway of Keelung harbour, is a legend landmark of Keelung and is an important military fortress of history. It was wrecked by many wars from 18 to 20 centuries. This island finally earned its peaceful life and current name after 1949.

Hoping Island is also a famous tourist spot of geological observation. Therefore, by using the story-telling approach, the third proposal is to design a picture book and related products with an adventurous story.

The authorities of Keelung City Cultural Bureau were impressed by these ideas and each family of products. With limit budget, they needed to select an appropriate design solution that can bring the best emotion perception and the highest marketing efficiency.

Figure 2: The proposal presentation of three different design solutions for Keelung.

4.2 Constructing the fuzzy judgment matrix

The decision process was followed by a series of evaluation conducted by a team with 8 decision-making members (DMs), including three Keelung citizens (domain-knowledge experts), two professors experienced in product design (design experts) and three tourists (potential customers). The process of determining the relative importance of major criteria (S.T.A.R.) is listed as follows. The original result of judgment matrix from 8 members is presented in Table 3.

【DM #1】				【DM #2】				【DM #3】				【DM #4】							
S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R				
S	1	LVs	LVs	LWk	S	1	LEs	LEs	LVs	S	1	LEs	LWk	LWk	S	1	LEs	LVs	Eq
T		1	Wk	Es	T		1	Eq	LWk	T		1	Wk	Wk	T		1	Wk	Wk
A			1	Wk	A			1	LWk	A			1	Wk	A			1	Wk
R				1	R				1	R				1	R				1

【DM #5】				【DM #6】				【DM #7】				【DM #8】							
S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R	S	T	A	R				
S	1	Wk	Eq	LWk	S	1	Es	LWk	LEs	S	1	LVs	LVs	LEs	S	1	LVs	LEs	LWk
T		1	LWk	LEs	T		1	LEs	LEs	T		1	Eq	Es	T		1	Wk	Es
A			1	LWk	A			1	Eq	A			1	Es	A			1	Wk
R				1	R				1	R				1	R				1

where L=Less.

Table 3: The original judgment matrix

By applying the fuzzy numbers defined in Table 1. The fuzzy judgment matrix is presented in Table 4.

【DM #1】				【DM #2】				【DM #3】				【DM #4】			
<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{7}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{1} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & 1 & \tilde{3} & \tilde{5} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & 1 & \tilde{1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & 1 & \tilde{3} & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & 1 & \tilde{3} & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & \tilde{1}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & \tilde{3} & \tilde{3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{1}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$								

【DM #5】				【DM #6】				【DM #7】				【DM #8】			
<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{3} & \tilde{1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{5} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>S</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tilde{7}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & 1 & \tilde{1} & \tilde{5} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>T</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & 1 & \tilde{3} & \tilde{5} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{1}^{-1} & \tilde{3} & 1 & \tilde{3}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{5} & 1 & \tilde{1} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{7} & \tilde{1}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{5} \end{bmatrix}$	<i>A</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 & \tilde{3} \end{bmatrix}$								
<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{5} & \tilde{3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & \tilde{5} & \tilde{1}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{5} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	<i>R</i>	$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{3} & \tilde{5}^{-1} & \tilde{3}^{-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$								

$\lambda_{\max} = 4.0561$; $CI = 0.018708$; $RI = 0.90$; $CR = 0.020786 < 0.1$, The consistency ratio is acceptable.

Table 4: The fuzzy judgment matrix

The complete results of all criteria, including the final BNP values, were listed in Table 5.

4.3 Integrating the scores from different members

Then the weights of DM group and average weights were derived by geometric mean method suggested by Buckley (1985). Using Equation 2, one of the synthetic matrix elements, \tilde{a}_{12} is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{a}_{12} &= (\tilde{a}_{12}^1 \otimes \tilde{a}_{12}^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{12}^8)^{1/8} \\
&= ((\frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{7}, \frac{1}{6}) \otimes (\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{4}) \otimes (\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{4}) \otimes (\frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{4}) \otimes (2,3,4) \otimes (4,5,6) \otimes (\frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{7}, \frac{1}{6}) \otimes (\frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{7}, \frac{1}{6}))^{1/8} \\
&= ((\frac{1}{8} \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6} \times 2 \times 4 \times \frac{1}{8} \times \frac{1}{8})^{1/8}, (\frac{1}{7} \times \frac{1}{5} \times \frac{1}{5} \times \frac{1}{5} \times 3 \times 5 \times \frac{1}{7} \times \frac{1}{7})^{1/8}, (\frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{4} \times 4 \times 6 \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6})^{1/8}) \\
&= (0.304, 0.370, 0.452)
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the values of other elements can be derived. The complete synthetic matrix is as follows.

	<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>S</i>	1	(0.304, 0.370, 0.452)	(0.207, 0.245, 0.331)	(0.246, 0.303, 0.436)
<i>T</i>	(2.213, 2.704, 3.293)	1	(0.951, 1.235, 1.834)	(1.130, 1.476, 1.897)
<i>A</i>	(3.020, 4.083, 4.827)	(0.545, 0.810, 1.052)	1	(1.189, 1.609, 2.294)
<i>R</i>	(2.294, 3.303, 4.059)	(0.527, 0.678, 0.885)	(0.436, 0.621, 0.841)	1

4.4 Constructing the weight vector of evaluation criteria

To obtain the fuzzy weights of each criterion, Equation 3 is employed. The value of for \tilde{r}_1 is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{r}_i &= \left(\prod_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \right)^{1/n} = (\tilde{a}_{i1} \otimes \tilde{a}_{i2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{in})^{1/n}, \\ \tilde{r}_1 &= (\tilde{a}_{11} \otimes \tilde{a}_{12} \otimes \tilde{a}_{13} \otimes \tilde{a}_{14})^{\frac{1}{4}} \\ &= ((1 \times 0.304 \times 0.207 \times 0.246), (1 \times 0.304 \times 0.207 \times 0.246), (1 \times 0.304 \times 0.207 \times 0.246))^{\frac{1}{4}} \\ &= (0.353, 0.407, 0.505)\end{aligned}$$

Likewise, remaining \tilde{r}_i can be derived.

$$\tilde{r}_2 = (1.242, 1.490, 1.840)$$

$$\tilde{r}_3 = (1.183, 1.519, 1.848)$$

$$\tilde{r}_4 = (0.852, 1.086, 1.318)$$

For the weight of each criterion, the authors used Equation 4. For \tilde{w}_1 , the result is:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{w}_1 &= \tilde{r}_1 \otimes (\tilde{r}_1 \oplus \tilde{r}_2 \oplus \tilde{r}_3 \oplus \tilde{r}_4)^{-1} \\ &= (0.353, 0.407, 0.505) \otimes (1 / (0.505 + 1.804 + 1.848 + 1.318), \\ &1 / (0.407 + 1.490 + 1.519 + 1.086), 1 / (0.353 + 1.242 + 1.183 + 0.852)) = (0.064, 0.090, 0.139)\end{aligned}$$

Likewise, the matrix of remaining \tilde{w}_i is obtained.

$$\tilde{w} = \begin{matrix} S \\ T \\ A \\ R \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} (0.064, 0.090, 0.139) \\ (0.225, 0.331, 0.507) \\ (0.215, 0.337, 0.509) \\ (0.155, 0.241, 0.363) \end{bmatrix}$$

4.5 Defuzzification and Normalization

To obtain the BNP value of the fuzzy weights of each criterion, the authors used Equation 7 to calculate DF_{w_1} .

$$\begin{aligned}DF_{w_1} &= \frac{(u_{w_1} - l_{w_1}) + (m_{w_1} - l_{w_1})}{3} + l_{w_1} \\ &= \frac{(0.139 - 0.064) + (0.090 - 0.064)}{3} + 0.064 = 0.0979\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the weights for the remaining criteria can be obtained. Moreover, for comparison of the importance of different criteria, the authors employed Equation 8 to normalize the weight vector for criteria. The defuzzified weights of major criteria DF_{wp} and its normalized values NW_p are shown as follow.

$$DF_{wp} = \begin{matrix} S \\ T \\ A \\ R \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.0979 \\ 0.3544 \\ 0.3537 \\ 0.2530 \end{bmatrix} \quad NW_p = \begin{matrix} S \\ T \\ A \\ R \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.0924 \\ 0.3347 \\ 0.3340 \\ 0.2389 \end{bmatrix}$$

4.6 Overall weights

After the weights for all criteria are computed, Equation 9 is used to calculate the overall level hierarchy weight. The value of \tilde{w}_1 is:

$$OW_{11} = NW_1 \times NW_{11} = 0.092 \times 0.376 = 0.035$$

The composite priorities of criteria were then determined by aggregating the weights throughout the hierarchy, and the final normalized BNP value were listed in Table 5.

<i>Criteria and Sub-criteria</i>	<i>Local weights</i>	<i>BNP</i>	<i>Normalized Weight</i>	<i>Overall weights</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
<i>Scenario Attractiveness</i>	<i>(0.064, 0.090, 0.139)</i>	<i>0.098</i>	<i>0.092</i>		
Immersive	(0.262, 0.373, 0.543)	0.393	0.376	0.035	11
Topical	(0.433, 0.627, 0.897)	0.652	0.624	0.058	10
<i>Tangibility</i>	<i>(0.225, 0.331, 0.507)</i>	<i>0.354</i>	<i>0.335</i>		
Lovable	(0.118, 0.181, 0.287)	0.195	0.183	0.061	9
Elegant	(0.236, 0.349, 0.567)	0.384	0.361	0.121	3
Conspicuous	(0.121, 0.188, 0.294)	0.201	0.189	0.063	8
Delicate	(0.170, 0.283, 0.401)	0.285	0.267	0.089	6
<i>Affection Satisfaction</i>	<i>(0.215, 0.337, 0.509)</i>	<i>0.354</i>	<i>0.334</i>		
Contended	(0.289, 0.406, 0.580)	0.425	0.407	0.136	2
Delightful	(0.213, 0.304, 0.445)	0.321	0.307	0.103	4
Prideful	(0.192, 0.290, 0.415)	0.299	0.286	0.096	5
<i>Reflection</i>	<i>(0.155, 0.241, 0.363)</i>	<i>0.253</i>	<i>0.239</i>		
Recallable	(0.238, 0.285, 0.421)	0.315	0.306	0.073	7
Sharable	(0.514, 0.715, 0.909)	0.713	0.694	0.166	1

Table 5: Weights of aspect and criteria for DMs group

4.7 Ranking the alternatives

The authors used the same process from 4.1 to 4.6 to obtain the evaluation value of each criterion for alternatives. Based on the evaluation results in Table 6, alternative A2 (Chinese Halloween Festival) is the best alternative.

<i>Sub-criteria</i>	Beer Festival at Bisha Fishing Port	Chinese Halloween Festival	Legend of Hoping Island
Immersive	0.0219	0.0091	0.0037
Topical	0.0128	0.0340	0.0109
Lovable	0.0090	0.0282	0.0241
Elegant	0.0178	0.0474	0.0555
Conspicuous	0.0398	0.0068	0.0166
Delicate	0.0096	0.0563	0.0235
Contended	0.0453	0.0453	0.0453
Delightful	0.0290	0.0338	0.0398
Prideful	0.0181	0.0563	0.0212
Recallable	0.0461	0.0193	0.0079
Sharable	0.0762	0.0651	0.0244
Total	0.3255	0.4015	0.2730
Ranking	2	1	3

Table 6: Ranking and evaluation value of each creitria for three alternatives

To sum up, by using pair-wise comparisons, with four criteria and eleven sub-criteria of emotional perception, the importance ratings of different criteria were determined. Furthermore, the pair-wise comparisons of three design solutions were also carried on each criterion derived from the major criteria of S.T.A.R. Then the fuzzy AHP was adopted to determine the weighted ratings of different alternatives of design solutions. The results showed that Chinese Halloween Festival turned out to be the best solution. While getting the final decision, the design team soon developed series of creative products. These products were then popularized to regional tourist exhibition. The fruitful results were reflected and reported on the newspaper headline (Figure 4). It demonstrated that the cultural creative products were able to promote the colorful culture of Keelung area.

Figure 4: The series products of Chinese Halloween Festival and a successful popularized feedback on the newspaper headline.

5. Conclusion

In order to develop the hierarchy of emotion, the authors conducted survey on relevant literature and collected data from interviewing experienced professors and designers. During the process of hierarchy formulation, the authors did encounter the problem of determining how many levels were necessary to express the complex structure of human emotion. In order to reduce the complexity of evaluation and follow the patterns of existing literature, three levels of hierarchy were employed. The depth and breadth of emotion hierarchy deserve more research efforts in the future.

In addition, the developed criteria of emotion were expressed either in noun at the second level or in adjective terms at the third level. Based on the observation, although these differences did not hamper the expression of opinions from the participant, the authors suggested that further research could investigate the differences in the interpretation and comprehension of terms from linguistic points of views.

This research proposed decision methods for selecting the concepts of cultural and creative produces that incorporate touching stories to convey profound cultural implication. Modern and fashionable identification and peripheral products were then developed through design profession. The authorities of Keelung City Cultural Bureau were impressed by some of the ideas and products proposed by college students and were seeking a closer relationship for academic-industry cooperation.

This case study had successfully demonstrated the capability of using FAHP to obtain weighted ratings from the results of pair-wise comparison of different emotion dimensions and alternative design solutions. With such a systematic approach, the decision of similar concept-selection problems can be made effectively and efficiently.

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